

Ayurveda Day to be marked on 23 September annually from 2025

Theme for Ayurveda Day 2025 is 'Ayurveda for People & Planet'

**Ayurveda is a Life Science rooted in Harmony with Nature:
Union Minister Shri Prataprao Jadhav**

Secretary Vaidya Rajesh Kotecha says, "Ayurveda Day has grown into global movement since 2016"

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For the first time since its inception in 2016, Ayurveda Day will be observed on a fixed date i.e. on 23 September – every year, as notified by the Government of India through a Gazette Notification issued in March 2025. Earlier, Ayurveda Day was celebrated on Dhanvantari Jayanti (Dhanteras). The decision to assign a fixed date marks a historic shift, giving Ayurveda a universal calendar identity and enabling greater participation at the global level.

Announcing the theme for this year's celebration – "Ayurveda for People & Planet" – the Union Minister of State (Independent Charge) for Ayush and Minister of State for Health & Family Welfare, Shri Prataprao Jadhav, said, "Ayurveda is not just a healthcare system, it is a science of life rooted in the principle of harmony between the individual and the environment. By designating 23 September as Ayurveda Day, India has given Ayurveda a global calendar identity. The 2025 theme, 'Ayurveda for People & Planet', reflects our collective resolve to harness the full potential of Ayurveda for global wellbeing and a healthier planet."

The Secretary, Ministry of Ayush, Vaidya Rajesh Kotecha, stated, "Since its inception in 2016, Ayurveda Day has emerged as a global movement celebrating India's traditional knowledge. The first all-India NSSO survey reaffirms that Ayurveda is the most

commonly used system of treatment across both rural and urban areas. The 2025 theme underlines our commitment towards advancing holistic health and ecological balance.”

The 9th Ayurveda Day (2024) was a landmark in India’s healthcare journey when the Prime Minister, Shri Narendra Modi, inaugurated Phase II of the All India Institute of Ayurveda (AIIA), New Delhi, launched four Centres of Excellence in Ayurveda, and introduced the nationwide “Desh Ka Prakriti Parikshan Abhiyan” campaign along with other health-related initiatives worth about ₹12,850 crore.

Building on this momentum, Ayurveda Day 2025 is envisioned not merely as a ceremonial occasion, but as a step towards positioning Ayurveda as a solution for contemporary global challenges such as lifestyle disorders, climate-linked diseases, and stress management.

The celebrations will include awareness campaigns, youth engagement programmes, wellness consultations, and international collaborations coordinated by the Ministry of Ayush and its institutions. Notably, activities in around 150 countries were organised in 2024 on Ayurveda Day, reaffirming Ayurveda’s growing global reach.

#AyurvedaDay2025
**Ayurveda for
People & Planet**

Did you know?

The Government of India has officially designated **23rd September** as the fixed date to celebrate **Ayurveda Day** every year. This decision, announced through a Gazette Notification on 23rd March 2025.

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Ayurveda Day

A Journey of Tradition to Global Recognition

2016 The Government of India started celebrating Ayurveda Day on the occasion of Dhanteras, marking it as **Dhanvantari Jayanti**.

For these years, Ayurveda Day was **observed every year on Dhanteras**, marking the occasion as Dhanvantari Jayanti. **2016 to 2024**

2025 **A historic moment!** The Government of India has designated **23rd September** as the fixed date for celebrating Ayurveda Day every year, symbolising balance in nature and life.

MV/GS/SG

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